

BECK'S GENERIC COGNITIVE MODEL (GCM) AND PROCESS-BASED THERAPY (PBT) IN THE TREATMENT OF TRANSDIAGNOSTIC PSYCHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

P. Rupondo,

January 2025, Copyright © Rupondo, P., Published 14 December 2025

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17929052

*Africa international University, Department of psychology, PhD in Clinical Psychology,
Clinical Neuropsychology*

KeyWords

Cognitive Model, Generic Cognitive Model, Aaron Beck, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, CBT, Schemas, Cognitive Triad, Transdiagnostic.

ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the evolution of cognitive theory and therapy, culminating in Aaron Beck and Haigh's (2014) Generic Cognitive Model (GCM). The discussion traces the historical foundations of the cognitive paradigm, from early contributions by William James, Ivan Pavlov, and B.F. Skinner to Beck's original cognitive model, which introduced the cognitive triad of negative views of self, world, and future in depression. The GCM is presented as a transdiagnostic framework, extending beyond depression to encompass a wide range of psychological disorders. Central features include the role of schemas, adaptive and maladaptive processes, and a dual-system model of automatic and reflective information processing. The incorporation of modes, belief systems, and stimulus-response dynamics enhances its clinical applicability and alignment with contemporary neuroscience. Nonetheless, critiques highlight potential mechanistic tendencies, limited attention to emotion regulation, and cultural biases. Despite these limitations, the GCM remains a significant advancement in cognitive therapy, offering a structured framework for case formulation and opportunities for refinement through empirical validation and integration with affective neuroscience.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cognitive therapies have evolved significant overtime since their development in the late 1800s. there have been numerous advancements in clinical applications, with one of the most significant developments being the generic cognitive model (GCM) by Aaron Beck in 1960, (Beck et al, 2014, Chad, et al, 2023). The model provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the connection between thoughts, emotions and behaviour with a major emphasis on cognitive patterns in emotions disorders such as depression, mood and bipolar disorders. This paper will review Beck and Haigh, (2014)'s article on the advances in cognitive theory and therapy and their generic cognitive model. In this review the writer will provide a brief historic background on the cognitive and behavioural paradigm, Beck's 1960 original cognitive model and an overview of Beck and Haigh's work. The writer will further critically analyse the paper, the recent advancements on the model, the key elements, implications and contributions post modernistic and meta modernistic therapeutic treatment.

2. HISTORY OF COGNITIVE PARADIGM AND COGNITIVE MODELS

The early foundations of cognitive behavioral science were laid in the 1890s by William James and his ideologies on functionalism and the role of cognition in human behaviour. He believed that consciousness and cognition operate as the adaptive functions that assist human beings in their daily living, (Chad, et al, 2023). In the same period, Ivan Pavlov emerged with his ideologies on stimuli - response (S-R Bond) and how this process triggers learned responses, (Ruggiero et al, 2018, Beck et al, 2021). Pavlov did experiments on dogs to test his ideologies, which led to the birth of classical conditioning. The pioneering of cognitive science brought the birth of behaviourism paradigm in 1913 through John B. Watson who built on the work of Pavlov, (Benjamin et al, 2011). Watson applied classical conditioning on human behaviour, through the "Little Albert" experiment in 1920, therefore shifting the ideology of cognition to observable phenomenon. In the 1930s B.F Skinner emerged with his principles of operant conditioning, which focused on reinforcement and punishment to shape behaviour, (Ruggiero et al, 2018).

The 1950s saw the birth of the rational emotive behavioural interventions by Albert Ellis, who emphasised the significance of beliefs in emotions and behavioural functioning, this became the foundation to the emergence of cognition and interventions. During the period of 1960 and 1980, cognitive behavioural interventions were born, with the emergence of Aaron Beck, and his propositions on maladaptive thinking patterns as significant contributors to emotional disorders, (Beck et al, 2021). In his publication on the advances in the in the Archives of General Psychiatry., in 1960-1969, Beck published his Generic Cognitive Model, which became the first model of cognitive behavioural therapy and the most widely recognised in history, (Beck et al, 2014; Beck et al, 2021).

While Beck was working on maladaptive patterns, Donald Meichenbaum emerged, in 1977 with the cognitive behavioural modification model which placed a significant emphasis on self-instructional training. The integrative approaches in cognitive and behavioural intervention techniques became popular therefore solidifying cognitive behavioural therapy as a leading treatment model for mental health disorders, (Tiba, 2024). Post modernistic and meta modernism period known as the third wave, saw the expansion of the cognitive and behavioral school of thought with the emergence of intervention advancement such as dialectical behavioural therapy by Marsha Linehan and Steven Heyes' acceptance commitment therapy. The advancement in neuroscience and technology had seen the refinement of the cognitive paradigm in interventions and integrative approaches such as mindfulness. To this day the cognitive paradigm and its intervention models have remained relevant in clinical settings.

3. OVERVIEW OF AARON BECK'S ORIGINAL COGNITIVE MODEL

Beck's original cognitive model for the past 5 decades has provided an evidence-based treatment modalities for case conceptualisation and treatment of emotional disorders and other mental health spectrums, (Beck et al, 2014). Tiba, (2024), describes this original model of cognitive behavioral interventions as the gold

standard of treatment of emotional related disorders. Beck's original model changed how practitioners perceived emotional disorders through the introduction of cognitive distortions in shaping emotional and behavioural factors. He stated that persons affected by emotional disorders such as depression or anxiety formed a cognitive triad (thoughts, feelings, actions) which represented the negative view about self, world and future. Beck describes this as the "fuel for distress", (Beck, et al, 2021).

Figure 1- Illustration of Beck's 1967 Cognitive Triad, (Beck, et al, 2021)

4. BECK AND HAIGH'S GENERIC COGNITIVE MODEL

Beck and Haigh (2014) present the generic cognitive model (GCM) as an evolution of Beck's 1967 original cognitive model. The GCM aims to provide a comprehensive framework for understanding and treating psychological disorders such as emotional disorders. The writing outlines the theoretical underpinnings of the GCM and its applications in the clinical intervention environment. The updated GCM provides a framework for addressing significant questions regarding the occurrence of mental disorders, maladaptive and adaptive functioning, the mental schema and attention as well as the dual information processing. Beck and Haigh's model features concepts on modes and the schemas important for expectancies, individual evaluations as well as the concept of memory and rule formation. The writer presents an applied model which serves as a template for specific disorder treatment and clinical case formulation. The template forms common principles that can be replicated and generalised across multiple spectrums of treatment.

Figure 2: Illustration of Beck & Haigh's 2014 Generic Cognitive Model

5. CRITICAL ANALYSIS

5.1 Key Components

Beck and Haigh (2014) present key components of their model. Firstly, the adaptation and maladaptation component which states that psychological disorders emerge from the adaptive processes and are critical in the process of adaptation. The GCM states that maladaptive cognitive patterns such as dysfunctional beliefs, biases in the processing of information and ineffective coping strategies manifest due to the exaggerated and rigid adaptation therefore causing dysfunction. Secondly, Beck et al, (2014), recognition of the role of schemas and their influence on the cognitive and behavioural responses in the daily functioning of individuals. Schemas are cognitive structures that assist people to organise and interpret information in daily functioning, (Hu, 2024). The concept of schemas was first systematically defined in a psychological developmental framework by Jean Piaget in 1926. Piaget identified that schemas evolve through the processes of what he termed assimilation and accommodation, therefore allowing individuals to construct knowledge and interact with their environment effectively, (Piaget, 1926, del Olmo Suárez et al, 2020). Beck et al, (2014), GCM model identify that people determine what is important and strive for progress and meaning through the schemas which are the key in processing daily stimuli to create order and interaction with other bodily systems, such as physiological systems. A

study by McVee and Dunsmore, (2023), explored the role of schemes in literacy studies, where the findings illustrated the comprehensive conceptions and applications involved, especially in processing and application of priori knowledge. Research further discovered that negative biased schemas cause the development of mental disorders such as anxiety, (del Olmo Suarez et al, 2020). Beck and Haigh's model further differentiate, between automatic (primal) and reflective (schema-driven) information processing known as the dual system. The GCM model recognises that schemas are critical in maintaining greater density and repeated activation which is the individual habitual behavior which also demonstrates the resilience and durability of schemas to transformation and change.

Another key element discussed in Beck et al, (2014), is the concept of stimuli response. The GCM as an interactive model identifies that reactions or responses are driven by goals and internal drives as well as events. These can be proactive or reactive in nature, where the feedback creates the interaction. It is important to note that the GCM concepts are derived from the Response theories of pioneers such as Ivan Pavlov classical conditioning and centralist ideologies of Albert Ellis irrational beliefs and B. F Skinner's operant conditioning with an emphasis on punishment and reinforcement. The GCM recognizes the role of the belief system in the functioning of an individual. Deriving from Beck's original model and the centralist ideologies of Albert Ellis, they state that belief is, represented by automatic thought patterns, (Beck, 1953, Beck et al, 2021, Chand et al, 2024). Primal beliefs affect conscious thought patterns when an individual is affected by depression or obsessive-compulsive disorders and they are further characterised by the level of biases, thus becoming maladaptive and resulting in clinical severe disorders. It is important to note that there is a progression from functional to dysfunctional (adaptive and maladaptive), when it comes to a belief system, based on the stimuli response that aligns with the level of vulnerability of an individual, (Beck et al, 2014, Chand et al, 2024).

Lastly, Beck and Haigh discuss the theory of modes as part of their GCM. They identify that while there is a wide range of psychological disorders, each one responds

to a different mode of cognitive organisation. They identified self-protective modes which exist in anxiety disorders and self-expansive modes in bipolar disorders, (Beck et al, 2014). Modes are networks of cognitive, affective and motivational components of behaviour that stimulate due to the striving for self-actualisation (life goals). Modes are the consolidated schema embedded beliefs as well as rules and prospects and complexities associated with self-esteem (self concept). Modes also integrate and share characteristics of individual schemas which include activation permeability and activation threshold associated with the relevant psychological issues. Beck and Haigh further outline clinical application of the GCM framework including case conceptualisation and disorder-specific strategies.

6. BECK'S ORIGINAL COGNITIVE MODEL VS. GENERIC COGNITIVE MODEL

Given the significant impact of Beck's cognitive models on understanding and treating psychological disorders, it is essential in this review to examine the differences between the two models, that is Beck's original 1967 model, which primarily focused on depression, and the 2014 Generic Cognitive Model (GCM), which expanded its application to a broader range of mental health conditions as outlined in Beck and Haigh's paper, (Beck et al, 2014). Aaron Beck's (1967) original cognitive model and the Generic Cognitive Model (GCM) of 2014 share foundational principles but differ in their scope and integration of cognitive processes, (Tsolakis, 2025, Beck et al, 2014, Beck, 1967). Firstly, the two models differ in scope and complexity. Beck's 1967 model emphasized on cognitive distortions and maladaptive schemas as the major influences on the development of emotional disorders. This was illustrated in the cognitive triad (negative view of self, world, and future). On the other hand, the GCM expanded on Beck's original model therefore incorporating a wider range of mental disorders, integrating cognition, emotional and behavioural components as well as the event (stimuli). Secondly the two models differ in the integration of cognitive processes. Beck's original model places and emphasis on automatic thought, intermediate beliefs, and the core schemas as the significant players in psychological distress, while Beck and Haigh incorporate metacognition as well as attention biases and emotional

regulation strategies thus creating a comprehensive treatment framework. Another difference is seen in the transdiagnostic approach, where Beck's original model was applied specifically for depression and then later adapted for anxiety and other mood disorders. Beck's original model was developed before the advancement in neuroscience but however had a significant impact becoming a gold standard of the post modernistic era. Ot date, (Tiba, 2024). The GCM is a unified cognitive model applicable across diverse psychological conditions and is an integrative approach from cognitive to behavior to social and neuroscience. The GCM allows an integrative framework that is beyond the traditional CBT model of treatment.

7. DISCUSSION

The GCM aligns with current research studies in cognitive-affective and cognitive neuroscience, specifically in relation to the dual-process models of cognition (Evans & Stanovich, 2013). The automatic versus reflective processing framework parallels distinctions found in the heuristic-systematic model of Chen & Chaiken, (1999) and Kahneman's (2011) work on fast and slow thinking processes. The strength of the GCM model lies in that it is holistic in nature and posits everyday psychological problems and clinical disorders as accentuation of normal adaptive functioning. It further builds on decades of neurobiology and information processing research, thus offering a strong empirical foundation. The model also provides a structured approach to case formulation which further enhances treatment precision. The role of schemas in psychopathology is supported by research on implicit cognition, which illustrates how deep-seated belief systems shape perception and behavior, (Tsolakis, 2025). The GCM is a unified cognitive model applicable across diverse psychological conditions and is an integrative approach from cognitive to behavior to social and neuroscience.

While components of the model have empirical backing from previous models the GCM lacks empirical testing and a unified model. It has not yet been rigorously tested in its entirety. Critics argue that the GCM may be overly reliant on the mechanistic approach, focusing heavily on cognitive processing, therefore possibly overlooking the holistic experience of patients, including emotional and cultural factors.

The model has been criticised for its insufficient focus on emotion regulation processes and strategies, which are critical in addressing vast psychological disorders, (Tsolakis, 2025). The model speaks of integration but however remains largely based on Western conceptualizations of cognition and may not fully account for cultural variations in psychopathology. Despite acknowledging affective factors, the model remains mainly cognitive and does not entirely integrate emotional and somatic or physical components, (Chad et al 2024). Alternative models such as the Process-Based Therapy (PBT) approach by Hofmann and Hayes (2019) proposed an integrative and flexible approach in transdiagnostic methodologies for psychological treatment, challenging the disorder-specific nature of Beck's framework, (Hoffman, et al., 2019).

8. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The GCM is a valuable resource in the treatment modalities of psychological disorders. However, the future research focused on testing the full GCM across diverse populations, particularly in non-Western settings, to validate its universality and adaptability can benefit larger populations in diverse cultures. Additionally, integrating affective neuroscience findings on emotion regulation could refine the model's applicability to emotion-driven disorders, (Gross, 2015). Beck and Haigh's Generic Cognitive Model (GCM) provide a robust and structured framework for understanding and treating psychological disorders by focusing on cognitive processes and their role in mental health. The integration of findings from affective neuroscience, specifically on emotional regulation, holds the potential to further refine the GCM's pertinence, especially in the treatment of emotional disorders. As the cognitive paradigm continues to progress, ongoing integration of these perspectives promises to enhance the overall efficacy and adaptability of therapeutic interventions that contribute to positive mental health outcomes of those affected by the illnesses.

REFERENCES

- Beck, A. T., & Haigh, E. A. P. (2014). Advances in cognitive theory and therapy: The generic cognitive model. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology, 10*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-032813-153734>
- Beck, A.T. (1967). *Depression: Clinical, Experimental, and Theoretical Aspects*. Harper & Row.
- Beck, J. S., & Fleming, S. (2021). A brief history of Aaron T. Beck, MD, and cognitive behavior therapy. *Clinical Psychology in Europe, 3*(2), e6701. <https://doi.org/10.32872/cpe.6701>
- Benjamin, C. L., Puleo, C. M., Settiani, C. A., Brodman, D. M., Edmunds, J. M., Cummings, C. M., & Kendall, P. C. (2011). History of cognitive-behavioral therapy in youth. *Child and Adolescent Psychiatric Clinics of North America, 20*(2), 179–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chc.2011.01.011>
- Chand, S. P., Kuckel, D. P., & Huecker, M. R. (2023). *Cognitive behavior therapy*. In *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing. Retrieved from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470241/>
- del Olmo Suárez, E., & Fernández-Pampillón Cesteros, A. M. (2020). A new approach for extracting the conceptual schema of texts based on the linguistic Thematic Progression theory. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.07440*.
- Gross, J. J. (2015). *Emotion regulation: Conceptual and practical issues*. In J. J. Gross (Ed.), *Handbook of emotion regulation* (2nd ed., pp. 3–24). The Guilford Press.
- Hofmann, S. G., & Hayes, S. C. (2019). The Process-Based Therapy approach: A transdiagnostic framework for psychological treatment. *Clinical Psychology Review, 69*, 42–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2019.01.003>
- Hu, W. (2024). Use of Schema Theory in the Teaching of English Reading Comprehension in Senior High School. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Public Administration, 3*(3), 320–325.
- McVee, M. B., & Dunsmore, K. (2023). *Schema Theory Revisited*. *Review of Educational Research, 75*(4), 531–566.
- Piaget, J. (1926). *The Language and Thought of the Child*. Harcourt, Brace & World.
- Beck's Generic Cognitive Model (GCM) And Pro-Cess-Based Therapy (PBT) In the Treatment of Transdiagnostic Psychological Conditions, Copyright © Rupondo, P., Published 14 December 2025
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17929052

- Ruggiero, G. M., Spada, M. M., Caselli, G., et al. (2018). A historical and theoretical review of cognitive behavioral therapies: From structural self-knowledge to functional processes. *Journal of Rational-Emotive & Cognitive-Behavior Therapy*, 36, 378–403. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10942-018-0292-8>
- Tiba, A. I. (2024). The grounded cognition foundation of the first cognitive model in cognitive behavior therapy: Implications for practice. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1364458>
- Tsolakis, P. (2025). Beck's Cognitive Model of Depression: Evolution, Modern Evidence and Critical Appraisal. *Psychology*, 16(1), 12–25. <https://doi.org/10.4236/psych.2025.161002>